

Building Resilience to Climate Change in Angola's coastal cities

Presented by

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Development Workshop Angola

to the

Angola Forum 2020

Sustainability & Inclusion in Economic Recovery & Reform

Chatham House - London 24 November 2020

Project Objectives - Climate Change, Water Supply in Coastal Settlements of Post-War Angola

- Improve knowledge about the climate and hydrology in coastal areas of Angola by filling the data gaps in order to understand trends and variability.
- Improve information about settlement patterns and population in four of Angola's urban coastal cities, housing over 10 million people. Assess the risks, impact and vulnerability from flooding and erosion at present and under future climate scenarios.
- Create tools for adaptation planning in Angola's urban coastal cities, especially for vulnerable social groups, and develop options for better water and settlement management.

Post-War Angola

- During the conflict, millions of Angolans fled the countryside for the relative safety of crowded shantytowns in coastal cities.
- The poor often settled in flood-prone environmentally risky sites, building homes incrementally where land was cheap.

Coastal Settlements at Risk: climate variability & water supply challenges

Angolan coastal settlements, house 64% of the Angola's urban population, are confronted by the dual challenge of

- supplying their war-displaced populations (particularly the poorest) with adequate water supply and safe housing.
- while at the same time confronting new problems of adapting to the climate and environmental changes that are occurring in these highly vulnerable coastal areas.

Mortality due to the high environmental risk

Fatalidades atribuíveis a questões ambientais (Fonte: Human Development Report, 2011.)

Findings from the Recovery of lost data

- The project's research team has recovered and analysed historical rainfall data; then digitalising it for sharing in the public domain.
- Luanda: the years with more than 600mm of rainfall causing severe flooding:
 - 1879 a 1900 0
 - 1901 a 1950 4
 - 1951 a 2000 9
- Mapping the results demonstrates the dramatically increased rainfall variability.

Developing Participatory Risk Mapping Tools

Building Geographic Information Systems

Participatory and spatial mapping

Remote sensing and digital modeling

Demographic Modelling using roof-counting & co-production of household information

Assessment of Types of Environmental Risks

Areas and types of flooding

More than 60 metres

- Buracos
- Desabamento
- Desabamento/lagoa
- Lagoa
- Lago
- Ravinas e inundação
- Águas estagnadas

Slopes

- <15m
- 15 – 30m
- 30 -45m
- 45 – 60m
- >60m

Municipal Adaptation Planning in 4 cities

- Risk maps and physical planning information were co-produced and validated with the participation of local communities and municipal government administrations on-the ground.
- The maps are essential tools being used for the planning of adaptation strategies with the aim of reducing climate risks of vulnerable urban communities.
- Municipal authorities who are responsible for delivering adequate and affordable services to their constituencies need regular and reliable information in useable and easily understandable forms.

Community participation in neighbourhood adaptation planning

- Participatory planning of informal settlements prevents the construction of new homes in flood-prone basins
- Promotes the greening and protection of drainage courses and slows run-off.

Emergency Action Against COVID-19

- Maintaining access to water supply for Angola's most vulnerable families, living in high-density slums (where the Corona virus is spreading quickly) is essential.
- DW has supported community water committees and trained water managers in peri-urban neighbourhoods .
- During the COVID-19 pandemic, the community water managers provide hygiene and safety information, but it has become a high-risk activity.

Conclusions

- **Low-lying African coastal cities disproportionately suffer environmental risks due to Climate Change.** They experience the increased risk of rising sea levels, the risk of flooding and strong tropical storms.
- **Data is still insufficient in post-conflict countries like Angola** for modeling and for disaster-preparedness plans. Information is vital for building adaptation strategies.
- **Urban planning in Angola** must incorporate climate change adaptation considerations, taking into account newly available information on variability risks.
- **Reduce Vulnerability of communities themselves can be promoted through micro-planning** and co-participation with municipalities to develop adaptation plans, resilient to climate change and natural disasters.

An aerial photograph of a densely packed urban area, likely a favela or informal settlement. The buildings are small and closely packed, with a clear grid-like street pattern. The colors of the buildings are muted, mostly in shades of grey, brown, and tan. The overall appearance is one of a highly organized yet tightly packed community.

Obrigado

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